

University Marine Energy Research Community

2023 Conference

4-6 October | Durham, NH, USA

Understanding the Uncertainty in the Technical Performance Level Assessment for Wave Energy

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Abstract

In recent years, the design and development of wave energy converters (WECs) has been explored with intense interest, with highly varying design concepts emerging globally across both research enterprises and industry. The design space for WECs is vast—many concepts ranging in functionality, control systems, power development systems, materials, and scale have been ideated and prototyped, but WEC technology has yet to converge. One critical element of the technology trajectory that governs the speed of adoption is the *performance* of a WEC concept. In analogous but more-established industries (such as aerospace, and environmentally sustainable electronics design), performance assessment is a quantitative method, based on historical data, that is used as an iterative tool to improve the design of these systems early on in the design process. Though more nascent than these approaches, in wave energy R&D, WEC performance has been assessed using the Technology Performance Level (TPL) assessment, which provides designers with a quantitative score, situating a grid-scale WEC concept on a scale from 1-9 (1 being the lowest performance, and 9 being the highest, trending with the oft-used Technology Readiness Level, or TRL). The TPL assessment is designed to be used during design iteration, when a WEC concept is fully ideated, to enable designers to consider potential means of improving the downstream performance of the concept. One concern that may be slowing the adoption of TPL among WEC developers is the inherent uncertainty in the assessment, and how uncertainty in the individual questions asked as part of the assessment may contribute to perceived inaccuracies in the final score. In this work, we explore the uncertainty present in the assessment and quantify this uncertainty using both traditional mathematical operations and a Monte Carlo simulation. Results imply areas of improvement of the TPL assessment, where reducing uncertainty will be most helpful to end users, enabling both TPL practitioners and users to understand with more accuracy those design elements that can be improved to impact device performance most substantively.

Keywords: Wave Energy, Wave Energy Converter Design and Analysis, Techno-Economic Analysis

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1. Introduction

Converting the mechanical energy of ocean waves into usable electricity or other forms of energy has varying, often significant potential across the world [1]. Estimates of global technical energy potential such as those by Sims et al. (500GW capacity) and Krewitt et al. (20EJ/yr, 639GW) alongside regional analyses from all different parts of the world [2–7], and the potential to use wave energy in emerging markets such as ocean observation or desalination [8] motivate continued research and development of wave energy devices. Design and development of those devices has not yet advanced far enough to reach the estimated potential power generation. The many reasons for the current state of the technology are identified and examined in multiple design studies and reviews [9–11] which emphasize that effective design and development of wave energy converters (WECs) will require assessment strategies that capture the many requirements of wave energy and can enable design decision-making [12–15]. Such holistic assessment strategies tend to contain high uncertainty due to their breadth and inclusion of qualitative aspects of the technology. Yet, simultaneously, it is that breadth which makes the assessments appealing for use by decision-makers. It is, therefore, important to characterize uncertainty in assessment to ensure that decisions are made with the best information possible.

The Technology Performance Level (TPL) assessment is a tool which has the potential to enable design decision making through holistic assessment [9,16–20]. TPL is a qualitative rating of a WEC concept's technoeconomic performance potential, which is determined through guided expert assessment [21]. TPL, conceptually and as an assessment tool, was developed to provide a method of assessment which can be used alongside the more commonly implemented Technology Readiness Level (TRL) [22]. TRL represents readiness towards commercial operation, and denotes the maturity of a technology under development, i.e., its development stage, rather than its quality, technical, or economic performance. Using both TPL and TRL ratings can help to ensure the technoeconomic performance potential of a device before it is pushed through costly development stages [22].

The work to date on the TPL assessment includes initial stakeholder analysis which enabled researchers to determine which factors were important to consider in a holistic assessment [23], the architectural design of the assessment [21], further interrogation of the categories and questions in the assessment to improve accuracy [24], initial work toward duplicating the assessment for use in emerging markets [25], use of the assessment's requirements structure in the development of conceptual design tools [26], and the conversion of the original Microsoft Excel-based assessment to a digital format [27]. Versions of the TPL Assessment have been used to assess the technoeconomic potential of WECs at various stages of development, including those submitted to the 2015–2016 Wave Energy Prize [28,29], deployed at the European Marine Energy Center, tested through the MaRINET project, and tested and/or researched through U.S. DOE's TEAMER program. The assessment was used in publications by Cordonnier et al. [30], Fernandez-Chozas et al. [31], and Costello et al. [32]. Despite the significant amount of work on the TPL Assessment, it remains, as Bertram et al. state, "difficult to use as a metric" [33], partially owing to its uncertainty.

Although the assessment has not been entirely adopted as a primary performance metric [10], it has been used with many industry developers, both to get developer feedback and as a means of determining opportunities for technology improvement at an early development stage. TPL is currently the most comprehensive single assessment of performance for WECs. Given the TPL assessment's current and future uses, it is important that we quantify the uncertainties in the assessment such that when comparing devices or using the results of the assessment to make development or funding decisions, designers and assessors understand the limitations. In this paper, we take the first step in addressing the challenge of TPL assessment uncertainty by both quantifying and qualifying that uncertainty.

In this work, we examine the scoring, weighting, and aggregating processes inherent to the architecture of the TPL assessment to qualify and quantify the uncertainty inherent in the approach. We give a summary describing the internal architecture of the TPL Assessment, and perform uncertainty quantification to describe the parametric uncertainty within the chosen architecture and the implications of that uncertainty on the confidence intervals of the final TPL score, as well as important intermediate scores. We show how uncertainty propagates using an analytical approach (mathematical rules) and using Monte Carlo Simulations. Finally, we discuss recommendations for further understanding and decreasing the uncertainty inherent in the tool.

Uncertainty and Uncertainty Quantification

The assessment of uncertainty and uncertainty quantification have been widely applied in engineering design. In this context, *uncertainty* is a means of defining the accuracy of a model or numerical analysis in representing physical phenomena, computational simulation, or experimental data, where lower uncertainty (and resulting higher accuracy) are preferred. Numerical modeling like the TPL assessment—which is the focus of this paper—has both *model* and *parametric* uncertainty: model uncertainty is due to the empirical generation of the numerical model and signifies

inaccuracy in the model itself; and parametric uncertainty is due to inaccuracy in the input values in the numerical model, often due to a lack of knowledge or credible information to validate inputs. In the case of the TPL assessment, model uncertainty is the inaccuracy of the scores of the assessment in terms of how they indicate potential performance. Parametric uncertainty is the inaccuracy of the assigned score in terms of its characterization of the WEC. Both the model and parametric uncertainties of the TPL assessment are *epistemic*, a classification of uncertainty that suggests the uncertainty is reducible through additional experience, knowledge, and data, and isn't inherent in the system.

TPL Assessment Structure

The TPL assessment has been previously described in [34], and the latest version is described in [5]. In practice, established experts in WEC technologies undertake an in-depth, multi-day training to learn how to administer the TPL assessment. The trained WEC expert assessor then reviews extensive documentation provided by the WEC technology developer guided by a WEC technology intake form and—based upon the provided information and any dialog with the developer—enters individual scores for each question in the tool. The tool ultimately generates a single numerical rating on a scale of one to nine; the latter representing the highest technoeconomic potential. The final score of the assessment (often called simply the “TPL”), as well as some of the intermediate scores—such as those in individual capabilities—have uncertainties which have yet to be determined. The assessment consists of 88 assessor questions distributed over 19 individual “sub-sub-capabilities” and 14 “sub-capabilities.” Each of the sub-capabilities falls into one of seven “capabilities,” which are grouped into three categories prior to determining a single TPL score. Capability-specific guidance for scoring is provided; defining *Low*, *Medium*, and *High* scores within the 1-9 range, with the associated numerical values for each of those ranges (most often) left to the assessor's discretion. In the most recent version of the tool, there is also additional guidance for interpreting the question.

To move from the individual question scores entered by the assessor to the final TPL score of the concept, the assessment tool employs both weights and combinations of those individual scores. Arithmetic means are used to combine scores that measure similar attributes; geometric means are used to combine scores that measure disparate attributes; and multiplication is used to combine multiple “must haves”[34]. The uncertainty in the assessor's input (parametric uncertainty) is therefore propagated through the assessment and can be expressed as an uncertainty in the final TPL score. Within some sub-capability and sub-sub-capability areas there are threshold scores. The thresholds indicate minimum scores that must be achieved within those sections to have a viable technology. Breaching a threshold generates a flag for the users of the assessment but does not result in additional penalties in the scoring calculation. Calculations of uncertainty will give users a better understanding of how likely it is that a technology will breach a threshold.

Uncertainty Propagation

We use two methods of estimating the parametric uncertainty throughout the TPL assessment: mathematical operations and Monte Carlo simulations. For the mathematical operations, we must assume that the input distributions are random, normally distributed, and independent. Given the current, limited knowledge regarding uncertainty of assessor input and the difference in expert knowledge across assessors, the assumption of random, normal distributions is acceptable, though it has some limitations. A normal distribution, is, by definition, continuous and infinite, whereas the inputs to the TPL assessment are discrete and constrained. Therefore, we use Monte Carlo simulations to quantify uncertainty based on discrete probability distributions that could be representative of assessor input distributions. In general, we believe the input uncertainties we have tested here are an accurate reflection of assessor input uncertainties.

Using the mathematical operations approach, we test input uncertainties of ± 0.5 , 1, 2, 3, and 4. For most questions, ± 0.5 is likely lower than the actual uncertainty, whereas ± 4 is likely higher. We include these to show extremes. For example, an assessor responding to the TRL 1-2 capabilities prompt, “What geophysical conditions are required to deploy this concept?” regarding a TRL 1-2 device where the foundation is not well defined might respond with a ‘6’, but reasonably have an uncertainty of ± 2 . For the Monte Carlo simulations, we create discrete probability distributions of scores for individual questions based on what we determined to be reasonable outcomes given our previous experience with the TPL assessment. In each discrete probability distribution, the input score will be within ± 1 of the correct score 75% of the time. For example, if the real score is 4, we assume the assessor chooses 4 about 35% of the time, 3 about 20% of the time, 5 about 20% of the time, and so on. We can expect, by comparing the mean to the real value given these distributions, that the TPL assessment would overestimate the final score for low-performing devices and underestimate the final score for high-performing devices. We test this assumption using Monte Carlo simulations.

Results

Mathematical Operations

The uncertainty propagation is different between capability areas. We see that the uncertainty in C_3 (*Grid Operations*) is equal to the uncertainty in the assessor input to the only question within the capability. Because there are no additional calculations, this capability area will tend to have the largest uncertainty. When the input uncertainty is ± 2 , the three remaining capabilities have an uncertainty of 2.0 for *Grid Operations*, 0.82 for *Benefit to Society*, and 0.67 for *Global Deployability*. We see that the equations for uncertainty of scores in *Grid Operations* and *Global Deployability* are the same-- the equation for uncertainty propagated through the arithmetic mean. The difference in the output uncertainty is due to the fact that there are eight questions inputted into *Global Deployability* and only one into *Grid Operations*. The number of questions, type of calculations, weights, number of sub-groups, and number of calculations all contribute to the differences in the capability uncertainties. The corresponding mean TPL uncertainties increase—as would be expected—with increasing input uncertainties. The standard deviations of TPL show that the impact of the TPL input score on the resulting uncertainty is minimal. For a mean input uncertainty of ± 2 , the final TPL score has a mean uncertainty of ± 0.21 , and a max of ± 0.47 . Given that a mean input uncertainty of ± 4 is likely high compared to real assessor uncertainty, we can determine that an uncertainty of ± 0.8 for the final TPL score is an approximate upper bound given the current assessment architecture.

Monte Carlo Simulations

To create the Monte Carlo simulation, three different uncertainty distributions are deployed (simulation cases RM3-1, RM3-2, and RM3-3; *RM3* refers to the reference model used in this work). For the feasible uncertainty distribution, we get an uncertainty of ± 0.83 , which is near the highest TPL uncertainty calculated by mathematical operations. The RM3-2 case results has an uncertainty of ± 0.37 , similar to the mean TPL uncertainty in the mathematical operations case in which the input uncertainty is ± 3 . The real solution for the RM3 TPL is 5.4, which is close to the mean of each RM3 simulation. The TPL error for the RM3-1 simulation is relatively symmetric around zero. This is because the RM3 is a mid-scoring concept, with a mode input score of 7. The means are closer to the real score for the mid-range scores. As scores tend to the extremes, the mean error of the input distribution increases, meaning that a low scoring concept would tend to be scored higher than it should, and a high scoring concept lower than it should. For a known input distribution, the Monte Carlo simulations will give the better estimate of the resulting TPL uncertainty compared to the mathematical operations. Unfortunately, we do not have data by which we can characterize the input distribution, so we have created one using our best judgement as experienced users and developers of the TPL assessment. In both the mathematical operations and the Monte Carlo simulations, we make assumptions about the input uncertainty. We believe that the assumptions made in the Monte Carlo simulations better reflect reality. Therefore, when using these results to make a rule-of-thumb estimate for what constitutes a meaningful difference between the TPL scores of two or more devices, we recommend using the more conservative estimate of uncertainty, ± 0.83 .

Discussion

We present the structure of the TPL assessment, determine expressions of the propagated uncertainty from assessor input to capability score then to final TPL score, and illustrate the anticipated resulting uncertainties of the final TPL scores. Before discussing the implications of this uncertainty, we should reiterate that what we are showing is the propagation of a theoretical parametric uncertainty through a model in which there exists model uncertainties which have not yet been quantified. In these simulations, our theoretical parametric uncertainty does not account for potential differences in parametric uncertainty across capabilities. These differences could be present for several reasons, including if 1) the general body of knowledge is greater for one capability rather than another, i.e., assessors have a better understanding of electricity generation than environmental impacts, leading to greater input uncertainty in capability five than capability one; 2) the guidance provided in the assessment is better for some capability areas than others; 3) the submission form which the designers and assessors use to provide information to the assessor includes more information relevant to some capabilities than to others; 4) WEC designers tend to focus on one capability over another such that some aspects of the WEC are more highly defined than others. It has not yet been determined if some questions/capabilities tend to have a greater parametric uncertainty than others.

Reducing both the model and parametric uncertainty of the TPL assessment will make the assessment more accurate and useful. Multiple iterations of the TPL assessment have centered on reducing user fatigue and improving the user interface, both of which make TPL more user-friendly. Model uncertainty in the TPL assessment can be reduced by finding means of validating the numerical model itself, and parametric uncertainty can be reduced by explicitly considering variation in user experience and redesigning the assessment and training materials to reduce biases and encourage convergence amongst assessors. It is more important to understand parametric uncertainty of the TPL

assessment when making comparisons between different devices, but, when making claims about a single device's performance potential, it is important to account for both model and parametric uncertainty.

Accounting for Uncertainty

There is a risk with the TPL score, and any other qualitative numerical rating system, that the end-user naively and inappropriately treats it as an objective, accurate, quantitative metric; for example, comparing values across time or technologies at an assumed precision and accuracy that this qualitative rating does not offer. This is the primary reason we need to both account for and be explicit regarding uncertainty in the TPL assessment. Secondly, accounting for uncertainty is important for truly novel device types and for the appropriate use of the threshold values feature of the assessment. Uncertainties unique to a device or device type may be amplified if the device is incongruent with the inherent assumptions of the tool – based upon what the architects have surveyed and understood to date. This means that users may experience high uncertainty when faced with a truly novel technology that does not “fit” into the inherent assumptions of the prompts. In both the case where this novel technology is a poorly conceived technology that violates first principles and, at the opposite extreme, in the case where the technology is exceedingly promising but alien to the field, the current assessment does not provide a sense of the lower or upper bounds of the potential performance of the technology to the decision maker because it does not provide an uncertainty estimate along with the final score. The tool may significantly over- and underestimate the technoeconomic performance levels, respectively. Estimating uncertainty is especially important for devices which are in the margins.

Reducing Uncertainty

Reducing uncertainty in the TPL assessment makes it more useful, improving descriptive accuracy, repeatability, and end-user confidence. As we have noted, model uncertainty for the TPL assessment is a measure of how accurately the assessment predicts a device's technoeconomic potential performance. The assessment structure reflects the architects' research and understanding of what factors are important to WEC performance and how important they are. Therefore, if one tried to reduce the uncertainty in the TPL assessment by changing the calculations within the assessment and thereby reducing the propagation of uncertainty, they would also be changing the model, and therefore changing the model uncertainty. This method of (seemingly) decreasing parametric uncertainty is not advisable. Any change to the calculations within the TPL assessment (the model) should be based on investigations of model uncertainty. These investigations will take time, as there is not yet enough data to correlate key capabilities to successful technologies. Yet, there are actions that could potentially lead to a reduction in parametric uncertainty.

To the extent possible, while balancing uncertainty with universal technology applicability, more precise guidance for the prompts would effectively decrease uncertainty in the final TPL scores. Currently, there are typically three tiers of guidance: “Low”, “Medium”, and “High” qualities provided as reference for the assessor; which are correlated to the numerical scores of 2, 5, and 8 [34]. However, on a 1-9 scale, more finely resolved guidance could reduce parametric uncertainty. Given the current, relatively immature state of the WEC industry—showing wide variation in technical configurations and operating principles—providing more finely resolved guidance while remaining concept-agnostic may not be realistic. Furthermore, adding more guidance may slow data entry.

Another potential way to decrease parametric uncertainty is to cross-reference the assessment questions with the potentially relevant sections of the technology submission that the designers and assessors complete together. This can help to ensure that for a given question, the assessor has considered the most important details of the WEC. In creating the cross-references, the TPL architects might observe areas where the submission form does not request enough details about the WEC.

Conclusions

We estimate that the parametric uncertainty for the final TPL score in the TPL assessment could range from ± 0.05 to ± 0.97 but is likely closer to ± 0.83 . We make these estimates by calculating the propagation of mathematical uncertainty through the TPL assessment simulated with random TPL score inputs and by running Monte Carlo simulations of the TPL assessment. The results of the Monte Carlo simulations tend to indicate a larger uncertainty than the propagation equations due to the assumptions made in order to use the propagation equations. These results indicate that a user should not draw conclusions about relative performance of two WECs which have a difference in TPL score less than 1.6. We examine the resulting uncertainty in each capability, showing that *Grid Operations* and *Permitting and Certification* scores have the highest uncertainty, and *Cost of Energy* the lowest. The range of capability uncertainties illustrates why they should be considered separately as well as aggregated in the final TPL score. We have provided the mathematical equations necessary for calculating the propagation of uncertainty in the TPL assessment. In the discussion, we have provided recommendations for quantifying, illustrating, and reducing uncertainty in the TPL assessment.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported in part by the United States Department of Energy through the Wave-SPARC and Lab Collaboration Project under grant DEEE0006816.0005. This work was, at least partially, funded by the U.S. Department of Energy's Water Power Technologies Office. Sandia National Laboratories is a multi-mission laboratory managed and operated by National Technology and Engineering Solutions of Sandia, LLC., a wholly owned subsidiary of Honeywell International, Inc., for the U.S. Department of Energy's National Nuclear Security Administration under contract DE-NA0003525. The National Renewable Energy Laboratory is operated by Alliance for Sustainable Energy, LLC, for the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) under Contract No. DE-AC36-08GO28308. This paper describes objective technical results and analysis. Any subjective views or opinions that might be expressed in the paper do not necessarily represent the views of the U.S. Department of Energy or the United States Government. The U.S. Government retains and the publisher, by accepting the article for publication, acknowledges that the U.S. Government retains a nonexclusive, paid-up, irrevocable, worldwide license to publish or reproduce the published form of this work, or allow others to do so, for U.S. Government purposes.

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